

<https://eurosciencegateway.eu>

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D1.3 Final summary of EuroScienceGateway main achievements, impacts, key results, sustainability data management and exploitation plans

Work Package 1

Technical References

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* *PU = Public*

PP = Restricted to other programme participants (incl. the Commission Services)

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CO = Confidential, only for members of the consortium (incl. the Commission Services)

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<i>1.0</i>	<i>20.08.2025</i>	<i>ALU-FR</i>	<i>Armin Dadras (ALU-FR), Oana Kaiser (ALU-FR), Björn Grüning (ALU-FR)</i>	<i>Sebastian Luna-Valero (EGI), Enol Fernandez (EGI)</i>

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Executive Summary

The EuroScienceGateway (ESG) project has successfully created a reliable, scalable, and collaborative Gateway, integrating European computational resources to facilitate data-intensive and FAIR-compliant research. The project achieved significant technical advancements by improving the Galaxy platform and expanding the Pulsar Network. Key innovations included the introduction of flexible resource integration models ("Bring-Your-Own-Compute" (BYOC) and "Bring-Your-Own-Storage" (BYOS)), significantly improving scalability and resource efficiency. Additional tools, such as the Galaxy Job Radar (GJR), administration dashboards, and an optimized job-scheduling algorithm (TPV Broker), further improved user experience, made deployment easier, and enhanced performance and sustainability.

User engagement increased throughout the project beyond the expectation. Looking at the stats of the European Galaxy portal, registered users grew from approximately 30,000 to over 130,000, while active monthly users doubled from around 3,000 to more than 6,000. This growth was supported by an extensive training and community-building program, comprising over 20 targeted online and onsite workshops.

ESG has significantly strengthened adherence to FAIR principles, contributing more than 20 workflows and over 40 tutorials, ensuring long-term usability through continuous maintenance by project partners. Scientifically, ESG resulted in over 10 peer-reviewed publications, underscoring its impact across disciplines.

Collaborations with over 20 European projects and initiatives enabled ESG's successful integration into the broader European research landscape. Furthermore, ESG backed the launch of six national Galaxy instances and more than ten Pulsar endpoints. This expansion broadens our reach, enabling an increasing number of researchers and computational infrastructures to leverage the project's outcomes. The primary data center, the European Galaxy instance, received ISO/IEC 27001 certification, emphasizing ESG's commitment to robust data security standards.

In conclusion, ESG has established a scalable infrastructure and a dynamic research community ecosystem, ready to sustain innovation and collaboration well beyond the project's formal duration.

List of Abbreviations

- **BYOC:** Bring-Your-Own-Compute
- **BYOD:** Bring-Your-Own-Data
- **BYOI:** Bring-Your-Own-Infrastructure
- **BYOS:** Bring-Your-Own-Storage
- **DOI:** Digital Object Identifier
- **ESG:** EuroScienceGateway
- **FDO:** FAIR Digital Object
- **GA4GH:** Global Alliance for Genomics and Health
- **GJR:** Galaxy Job Radar
- **GTN:** Galaxy Training Network
- **HPC:** High-Performance Computing
- **LS:** Life Science
- **PID:** Persistent Identifier
- **PMU:** Project Management Unit
- **SABER:** Systematic API Benchmark for (Pulsar) Endpoint Reliability
- **SIG:** Special Interest Group
- **TES:** Task Execution Service
- **TlaaS:** Training Infrastructure as a Service
- **TPV:** Total Perspective Vortex
- **TRL:** Technology Readiness Level

Table of contents

Disclaimer	3
Executive Summary	4
List of Abbreviations	5
1. Introduction and Scope of the Report	7
2. Overview of the ESG Project	7
2.1 Project Objectives	7
2.2 Consortium and Roles	15
2.3 Implementation Overview	15
3. Main Achievements, Key Results, and Impact	17
3.1 Technical Developments	17
3.2 Community Engagement and User Support	19
3.3 EOSC Integration and Interoperability	19
3.4 Adoption by scientific communities	21
4. Data Management	22
4.1 FAIR Data Practices and Policies	22
4.2 Data Sharing and Reuse	23
4.3 Long-term Data Stewardship	24
5. Sustainability and Exploitation Plans	24
5.1 Long-term Hosting and Service Maintenance	24
5.2 Governance and funding model	25
5.3 Exploitation by Beneficiaries and Stakeholders	25
6. Dissemination and Communication Activities	26
6.1 Key Dissemination Channels and Results	26
6.2 Community and Stakeholder Engagement	27
6.3 Visibility and Outreach	28
7. Conclusions	28
8. References	29

1. Introduction and Scope of the Report

This document provides a comprehensive summary of the ESG project's key achievements, impacts, sustainability and exploitation strategies, FAIR data management practices, and dissemination activities undertaken between September 2022 and August 2025.

The information presented is compiled from previously submitted deliverables, publicly accessible project documentation, datasets with Persistent Identifiers (PIDs), and feedback from consortium partners. This report demonstrates how ESG's outcomes align with the strategic objectives set forth in the project's Grant Agreement, Horizon Europe, and EOSC guidelines. Specifically, the report highlights ESG's contributions to enhancing interoperability, open science practices, infrastructure sustainability, and European research excellence.

2. Overview of the ESG Project

2.1 Project Objectives

The ESG project was designed to enhance European research by providing accessible, scalable, and interoperable computational resources to support pioneering data-driven research across diverse scientific domains. The project's objectives align with Horizon Europe and EOSC goals, addressing key challenges in computational infrastructure accessibility, job distribution efficiency, FAIR data compliance, and community adoption.

Objective 1: Accessible e-infrastructure resources for European scientists to enable pioneering data-driven research across scientific domains

ESG aimed to develop and deploy a robust workflow-based gateway integrating diverse European computing and storage infrastructures, leveraging the Galaxy platform and the distributed Pulsar network. Originally started in rapid response scenarios such as the COVID-19 pandemic, this infrastructure was developed to achieve a Technology Readiness Level (TRL-9), guaranteeing a fully operational service demonstrated through real-world use cases in biodiversity and climate sciences, materials science, and astrophysics. Actions included further developing a software to access heterogeneous computational resources and storage, improved by features such as the BYOC and BYOS models (see Figure 1).

Pulsar-Network
0.1

Search docs

PULSAR ENDPOINT CONFIGURATION

- Introduction
- Requirements
- Get RabbitMQ credentials
- Configure the pulsar endpoint
- Building the Pulsar endpoint
- Terraform variables details
- Multiple Pulsar services in one node

POST DEPLOYMENT

- Setting up extra Pulsar services after deployment
- Manual Removal of Extra Pulsar Services

SPECIAL TOPICS

- Benchmark
- GPUs
- Staging actions
- Jump host
- Oracle Cloud Infrastructure

ABOUT PROJECT

- Partners
- Status

Home / Welcome to Pulsar-Network's documentation! [View page source](#)

Welcome to Pulsar-Network's documentation!

The Pulsar Network is wide job execution system distributed across several European datacenters, allowing to scale Galaxy instances computing power over heterogeneous resources.

eosc | EuroScienceGateway

Currently, the Pulsar Network is developed in the context of the [Horizon Europe EuroScienceGateway project](#), enabling end-users to easily access and exploit remote compute resources, and resource providers to offer compute resources for scientific purposes through the Galaxy interface.

This documentation shows how to install and configure a Pulsar network endpoint on an OpenStack Cloud infrastructure and how to connect it to useGalaxy.* server. The same Pulsar endpoint can be associated to any Galaxy instance, if properly configured.

When you reach to the end of this document, you'll have an operational Pulsar endpoint running on your OpenStack tenant. The document covers from setting up of OpenStack details, and required steps to install the endpoint with Terraform on this created OpenStack space, using HTCCondor as

Figure 1. Documentation page of the Pulsar-Network

The expected outcomes were successfully achieved, with ESG infrastructure demonstrating compatibility with European computing providers, high-performance computing (HPC) capacities, and commercial cloud providers. The resulting middleware infrastructure, validated through diverse scientific use cases, enabled cutting edge research and collaboration. Furthermore, all methodologies and tools developed were documented comprehensively, with code openly accessible to foster broader community adoption.

Objective 2: Support the varieties of analysis types and diverse usage patterns through efficient and smart job distribution to appropriate and sustainable infrastructures.

ESG addressed the challenge of supporting varied analysis types and diverse user needs through intelligent job distribution strategies. The introduction of modular models such as BYOC and BYOS was key to achieving this flexibility, allowing researchers to efficiently integrate their local computational resources directly into the ESG ecosystem (see Figures 2 and 3). An important part of our design was the implementation of a smart, scalable job-scheduling service (the TPV Broker (Azab, Srikakulam, et al. 2025; Azab, De Geest, et al. 2025)) which leveraged a fuzzy algorithm trained on high quality data and continuously improved through operational usage. The TPV Broker incorporated data locality considerations, which can improve performance by executing data-intensive tasks directly on infrastructure co-located with storage resources (see Figure 4).

Figure 2. User-interface of Bring-Your-Own-Data on the European Galaxy server

Figure 3. User-interface of Bring-Your-Own-Storage on the European Galaxy server

Fuzzy matchmaking algorithm

Figure 4. TPV Broker architecture. Source: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.16312227>

The smart job distribution approach aimed to improve operational efficiency by allocating computational jobs to the destinations that meet job requirements and are less utilized, with the goal to evenly spread the load across sites in Europe. Although no quantitative evaluation is included in D4.2 or the related publication, monitoring tools such as the GJR and SABER (Systematic API Benchmark for (Pulsar) Endpoint Reliability)¹ were used to provide visibility into system behavior and support day-to-day operations (see Figure 5).

¹ <https://github.com/usegalaxy-it/saber>

Figure 5. Galaxy Job Radar (GJR) visualizing the job distribution of Pulsar Network across European infrastructure

Objective 3: The application of FAIR principles to workflows and adoption of FAIR Digital Objects to stimulate reusable and reproducible research and enable the EOSC Interoperability Framework.

ESG operationalized the application of FAIR principles in computational workflows and enabled the EOSC Interoperability Framework (EOSC-IF) through practical integration with FAIR Digital Objects (FDOs). ESG implemented EOSC-IF onboarding guidelines for workflows and research products by packaging workflows as Workflow RO-Crates with machine-actionable run provenance (Workflow Run RO-Crate) and persistent identifiers (PIDs), and by publishing workflow definitions to WorkflowHub for discovery and reuse (see Figure 6).

EuroScienceGateway Overview

Overview Related items

EuroScienceGateway will leverage a distributed computing network across 13 European countries, accessible via 6 national, user-friendly web portals, facilitating access to compute and storage infrastructures across Europe as well as to data, tools, workflows and services that can be customized to suit researchers' needs. EuroScienceGateway will deliver a robust, scalable, seamlessly integrated open infrastructure for data-driven research, contributing an innovative and customizable service for EOSC that enables operational open and FAIR data and data processing, empowering European researchers to embrace the new digital age of science.

Space: ELIXIR
WorkflowHub PALS: No PALS for this Team
SEEK ID: <https://workflowhub.eu/projects/166>
Team start date: 1st Oct 2022
Funding codes:
• <https://doi.org/10.3030/101057388>
Team end date: 31st Aug 2025
Public web page: <https://eurosciencegateway.eu/>

eosc
Euro
Science
Gateway

Annotated Properties

Topic annotations
Software engineering, Workflows

Figure 6. EuroScienceGateway page on WorkflowHub portal

For deposition and cross-repository discovery, ESG advanced and applied community standards so research products can be linked, validated, and exchanged automatically across infrastructures (see Figures 7–8). These practices deliver technical and semantic interoperability; coupled with federated AAI (EGI Check-in, LS Login, IAM4NFDI) and standards-based execution across distributed resources, they also meet organizational interoperability expectations within EOSC. In short, ESG does not just align with EOSC-IF; it executes it in production making workflows findable, accessible, interoperable, and reusable across EOSC services and communities.

Figure 7. Workflows can be exported as RO-Crate on the European Galaxy platform

Invoked Workflow: Find exons with the highest number of features (Version: 1)

invoked 3 months ago 7 of 7 steps successfully scheduled. Anton Nekrutenko Helena Rasche Armin Dadras

History: test job cache gta2025 5 of 5 jobs complete. workflow runs: 2

Overview Steps Inputs Outputs Report Export Metrics

Invocation Export Wizard

1 Select output format 2 Select destination 3 Export

Select where you would like to export the workflow invocation Research Object Crate to and click Next to continue.

Temporary Direct Download

Generate a link to the export file and download it directly to your computer.

Please note that the link will expire after 24 hours.

Repository

If you need a **more permanent** way of storing your workflow invocation you can export it directly to one of the available repositories. You will be able to re-import it later as long as it remains available on the remote server.

Examples of remote sources include Amazon S3, Azure Storage, Google Drive... and other public or personal file sources that you have setup access to.

RDM Repository

You can upload your workflow invocation to one of the available **Research Data Management repositories** here. This will allow you to easily associate your workflow invocation with your research project or publication.

Examples of RDM repositories include Zenodo, Invenio RDM instances, and other public or personal repositories that you have setup access to.

Figure 8. Multiple options to submit Workflows as RO-Crate to different destinations.

The outcomes include integration of FDOs within Galaxy as the workflow management system, reinforcing the EOSC interoperability vision and enabling verifiable reuse at scale (see Figure 9). ESG’s methodologies and reference implementations form a blueprint for reproducible research workflows, lowering adoption barriers and supporting uptake beyond the project’s immediate scope.

Figure 9. Workflow and its metadata visualization on Galaxy

Objective 4: Adoption of the EuroScienceGateway by researchers in diverse scientific disciplines.

Another objective of ESG was promoting broad adoption by researchers across various scientific domains. ESG’s strategy included comprehensive training programs, targeted dissemination, and community engagement. The project delivered over 20 workshops, engaging more than 10,000 participants, ensuring researchers effectively leveraged the ESG infrastructure. Domain-specific workflows developed and disseminated through WorkflowHub directly supported communities in biodiversity, climate sciences, astrophysics, materials science, and life sciences, demonstrating ESG’s versatility and direct relevance.

The ESG dissemination strategy included scientific publications, outreach blog posts, webinars, community-building activities, and active presence at relevant conferences. ESG maintained a dynamic online presence through its consortium website² and social media channels, increasing visibility and uptake. By combining outreach with robust technical solutions, ESG grew its active user base, surpassing original expectations and aiming for sustained service to over 130,000 users.

In conclusion, ESG fulfilled its objectives by delivering an accessible, federated, FAIR-compliant infrastructure supporting European research excellence. Its contributions

² <https://galaxyproject.org/projects/esg/>

have improved Europe's digital research capabilities, ensuring long-term sustainability, interoperability, and extensive adoption across scientific communities.

2.2 Consortium and Roles

The Albert Ludwig University of Freiburg coordinated ESG, collaborating with key European institutions including VIB VZW, EPFL, CESNET, BSC, UB, CNRS, UP, CNR, INFN, UNIFI, EGI, UiO, AGH-UST, IISAS, TUBITAK, UKRI, and UNIMAN.

The consortium adopted a flat governance structure, promoting inclusive decision-making to address infrastructure access challenges across Europe. Collaboration focused on architecture development, Galaxy platform improvement, Pulsar endpoint deployment, and dissemination of training materials.

2.3 Implementation Overview

The ESG implementation (Sep. 2022–Aug. 2025) was structured around five work packages:

- **WP1:** Project Management, Coordination and Dissemination
- **WP2:** Stimulate FAIR and reusable research
- **WP3:** Pulsar Network: Distributed heterogeneous compute
- **WP4:** Building blocks for a sustainable operating model
- **WP5:** Community engagement, adoption and onboarding

Major milestones included establishing national Galaxy instances and Pulsar endpoints (Nicotri et al. 2024; Dadras and Tangaro 2025), developing the TPV job-scheduling algorithm, implementation of Bring-Your-Own-Infrastructure (BYOI) model (Pedersen et al. 2024), onboarding FAIR-compliant workflows via WorkflowHub³, and successfully engaging early adopter scientific communities (Dadras et al. 2025; Nikolay 2024).

Governance

Governance was established at European Galaxy Days (Oct. 2022). The Project Management Unit (PMU), led by Freiburg University, ensured coherent coordination, reporting, and communication. Strategic decisions were managed by the General Assembly, with technical guidance from an Executive Board. Monthly virtual meetings and annual in-person events facilitated project progress, community feedback, and long-term sustainability planning.

Platform Improvement

³ <https://workflowhub.eu/>

ESG continuously improved the Galaxy platform by integrating new tools, supporting national Galaxy instances, deploying multiple Pulsar endpoints, and introducing the BYOI model:

- BYOC/BYOS: Allow flexible integration of external computational and storage resources.
- Bring-Your-Own-Data (BYOD): Facilitate data import and export from diverse repositories (e.g., S3-compatible stores).

Innovations also included the TPV Broker smart job-scheduling algorithm for optimized resource allocation, reducing operational costs and enhancing green computing practices (Azab, Srikakulam, et al. 2025; Azab, De Geest, et al. 2025). Monitoring dashboards (e.g., GJR⁴ and admin dashboards) increased operational transparency and efficiency.

FAIR Workflow Publication

ESG contributed to the update and development of FAIR workflows by publishing reproducible computational workflows (Soiland-Reyes et al. 2024; 2025) as scholarly outputs via WorkflowHub⁵. RO-Crate profiles ensured enriched metadata, versioning, and PIDs, enabling EOSC interoperability and sustainable reuse. Provenance tracking strengthened reproducibility, while outreach via international conferences and scholarly forums further established workflows as citable academic resources.

Training and Community Onboarding

Training was central to ESG's strategy, with more than 10,000 participants attending ESG workshops. The Galaxy Training Academies⁶ and Training Infrastructure as a Service (TlaaS)⁷ supported efficient, scalable delivery of structured, hands-on training sessions, promoting sustained platform adoption.

Community Engagement and Events

⁴ <https://gjr.metacentrum.cz/>

⁵ See registered workflows here: <https://workflowhub.eu/collections/13>

⁶ See Smörgåsbord 2023 <https://gxy.io/smorgasbord3>, Galaxy Training Academy 2024 (<https://gxy.io/GTN:F00005>) and Galaxy Training Academy 2025 (<https://gxy.io/GTN:F00026>)

⁷ See landing page: <https://usegalaxy.eu/tiaas/>

ESG actively participated in scientific conferences and community events⁸ (such as European Galaxy Days, domain-specific workshops, conferences, and hackathons), enhancing visibility and directly addressing community needs. These interactions led to technical development, built vibrant user communities, and promoted ESG's broad adoption.

3. Main Achievements, Key Results, and Impact

3.1 Technical Developments

The ESG project has delivered a federated, production-ready research infrastructure that significantly enhances Europe's computational research capabilities. Designed to lower the barriers to use compute infrastructure, ESG enabled scientists across disciplines to execute complex, data-driven workflows without requiring advanced technical expertise or access to local compute infrastructure.

At the core of ESG's technical contribution was the enhancement of the Galaxy platform to support a distributed, scalable, and FAIR-compliant computing environment. This was made possible through the development and deployment of an extensive Pulsar Network—a distributed job execution system spanning more than ten geographically dispersed endpoints across Europe. This network allowed access to heterogeneous compute resources, including cloud and HPC environments.

To maximize flexibility and user autonomy, ESG introduced modular infrastructure models: BYOC, BYOS⁹, and BYOD¹⁰. These innovations enabled researchers and institutions to integrate their local resources directly into the ESG ecosystem, allowing them to execute workflows close to their data, minimize latency, reduce costs, and optimize performance. The flexible integration approach enabled efficient resource utilization and contributed to environmentally sustainable computing practices.

Another technological advancement was the development of the Total Perspective Vortex (TPV) Broker, a smart job-scheduling algorithm. This scheduler dynamically distributes jobs across the Pulsar Network based on dynamic system metrics, data locality, and workload characteristics. By optimizing computational load distribution, the

⁸ For the comprehensive list of events see: <https://galaxyproject.org/projects/esg/events/> and <https://galaxyproject.org/projects/esg/news/?tag=esg-wp1>

⁹ See the tutorial here: https://training.galaxyproject.org/training-material/faqs/galaxy/manage_your_galaxy_storage.html

¹⁰ See the tutorial here: https://training.galaxyproject.org/training-material/faqs/galaxy/manage_your_repositories.html

TPV Broker improved resource efficiency, minimized execution times, and supported green computing objectives. Complementing this, the GJR dashboard provided visualizations of system performance and job statuses, enhancing operational transparency and user experience.

To support secure and interoperable access across institutional boundaries, ESG implemented federated authentication mechanisms including EGI Check-in, Life Science (LS) Login, and IAM4NFDI. These identity federation services enabled authenticated access to distributed resources, aligning ESG with broader EOSC interoperability goals.

Infrastructure deployment was improved by automation tools like the Infrastructure Manager, which simplified the setup of Galaxy and Pulsar environments through a browser-based interface. This approach reduced administrative overhead and significantly lowered the barrier for new partners to join the federated network.

ESG also supported the launch of several national Galaxy instances, including in France¹¹, Italy¹², Belgium¹³, Norway¹⁴, the Czech Republic¹⁵, and Spain¹⁶. These deployments are maintained by institutional partners under national or organizational mandates, ensuring long-term hosting and geographic diversity. Each instance operates as an entry point to the broader ESG infrastructure, providing researchers with access to advanced computational capabilities.

All infrastructure components were built upon open standards and accompanied by comprehensive documentation, version control, and reproducible deployment procedures. This commitment to openness ensures ESG's contributions can be reused, extended, and maintained across the EOSC ecosystem and beyond.

From a technological perspective, ESG delivered a mature and interoperable platform that transforms how research infrastructures are designed and operated. The use of community-driven standards such as the Global Alliance for Genomics and Health (GA4GH) Task Execution Service (TES) allowed Galaxy workflows to run across diverse EOSC-compliant infrastructures. These integrations position ESG as a key architectural component of EOSC, supporting seamless interoperation between data and compute services across Europe.

¹¹ <https://usegalaxy.fr/>

¹² <https://usegalaxy.it/>

¹³ <https://usegalaxy.be/>

¹⁴ <https://usegalaxy.no/>

¹⁵ <https://usegalaxy.cz/>

¹⁶ <https://usegalaxy.es/>

Moreover, ESG's technological stack has achieved a high level of operational maturity—demonstrated by the smooth execution of complex workflows, minimal downtime, and high user satisfaction. The ability to dynamically scale across a federated infrastructure, combined with ESG's smart scheduling and federated authentication, represents a substantial step forward in the delivery of reliable, scalable, and secure research services.

In summary, ESG's technical developments and infrastructure deployment have redefined the landscape of computational research infrastructure in Europe. Through its flexible architecture, automation tools, interoperable services, and commitment to openness, ESG has created a robust, user-centric platform. Its technological and infrastructural impact ensures long-term sustainability, easy replication, and continued growth as part of the evolving EOSC ecosystem.

3.2 Community Engagement and User Support

Community engagement and user support were key factors of ESG's approach, focusing heavily on capacity building, inclusive adoption, and sustained user involvement. Throughout its duration, ESG organized and conducted more than 20 comprehensive training events, workshops, and onboarding activities, collectively reaching over 10,000 participants across Europe.

To ensure effective and sustainable community integration, ESG developed structured onboarding resources, including the detailed Community Onboarding Cookbook. This guide facilitated the establishment of Special Interest Groups (SIGs)¹⁷, allowing domain-specific communities to collaborate effectively and sustainably. Over the project's duration, ESG significantly expanded the scientific topics on Galaxy Training Network¹⁸ from 23 initially to more than 30 active topics by project conclusion, highlighting its successful engagement strategy.

The training component was notably improved by providing TlaaS. TlaaS allowed instructors and trainees to utilize pre-configured compute environments, significantly reducing technical barriers and enhancing the quality and accessibility of training sessions. User support was continuously provided through regularly updated documentation, responsive communication channels, and active GitHub issue tracking, ensuring that both novice and experienced users received timely, high-quality assistance, further strengthening community trust and participation.

¹⁷ <https://galaxyproject.org/community/sig/>

¹⁸ <https://training.galaxyproject.org/>

3.3 EOSC Integration and Interoperability

The ESG project has made a substantial contribution to the EOSC by delivering mature, interoperable services that ensure FAIR principles, open science best practices, and federated research infrastructure. ESG not only integrated with EOSC's technical landscape but also contributed to its societal and policy objectives, aligning closely with the strategic ambitions of Horizon Europe.

At the technical level, ESG achieved full integration with the EOSC ecosystem through the implementation of FDOs and the RO-Crate packaging standard, facilitating the publication of structured, machine-actionable workflows enriched with PIDs, metadata, and provenance information. These workflows, published via WorkflowHub, achieved TRL-9, demonstrating production-grade maturity and ensuring their long-term discoverability, interoperability, and reuse across the EOSC infrastructure.

ESG further advanced interoperability by adopting globally recognized standards such as the GA4GH-TES, enabling the execution of Galaxy workflows across EOSC-compliant infrastructures. This commitment to open and federated standards ensures that ESG services are not siloed but instead participate in a broader, connected ecosystem of European and international research infrastructures.

Key to ESG's EOSC alignment was its implementation of federated identity and access management, integrating solutions such as EGI Check-in, LS Login, IAM4NFDI, and DataPlant AAI. These systems allow researchers to authenticate once and access services across institutional and national boundaries. This approach simplifies access, enhances data security, and ensures compliance with EOSC's interoperability framework.

Beyond technical contributions, ESG played an instrumental role in addressing socio-economic disparities within the European research landscape. By providing easy-to-use, open-access computational resources and infrastructure models—such as BYOI—ESG democratized access to digital research capabilities. This lowered the barriers for institutions and researchers, particularly those in under-resourced regions, to participate in cutting-edge, data-intensive science.

The adoption of federated models allowed researchers to contribute and consume resources equitably, helping bridge the digital divide across Europe. For example, smaller institutions or those outside traditional research hubs could integrate their infrastructure into ESG or leverage existing ESG resources without incurring major operational costs. This not only boosts their computational capacity but also facilitates collaborative, cross-border research at scale.

ESG also had a meaningful policy-level impact, operationalizing best practices in open science and FAIR data management. Its workflows, training materials, and data products were made openly available through trusted repositories such as Zenodo, WorkflowHub, GitHub, and the Galaxy Training Network (GTN)¹⁹. These efforts provide a replicable blueprint for how FAIR-compliant services can be implemented sustainably and adopted across scientific disciplines.

From a strategic perspective, ESG supported multiple priorities outlined in Horizon Europe and EOSC roadmaps. These include promoting open science, enhancing digital sovereignty, supporting cross-disciplinary collaboration, and building robust, federated European research infrastructure. ESG enabled researchers to perform advanced analyses without specific infrastructure or programming expertise requirement—thus expanding the reach and impact of European scientific institutes.

Through its use of open standards, interoperable services, and mature infrastructure components, ESG contributed to EOSC's goals of creating a federated, user-centric, and sustainable research ecosystem. The project helped elevate platforms such as WorkflowHub and the Pulsar Network from pilot prototypes to operational EOSC components, ensuring their long-term integration and scalability.

Moreover, ESG's infrastructure and governance models align with EOSC's sustainability principles. Its distributed service architecture avoids centralized bottlenecks and empowers institutions to maintain and evolve services according to local capacities and needs. This shared-responsibility model ensures resilience and cultivates a sense of ownership among participating institutions.

The project's influence extends to European research policy, demonstrating how technical and governance innovation can drive equal scientific access and enable alignment with digital transformation goals. ESG provides a good example of how investments in open, federated infrastructure translate into real-world benefits: improved scientific productivity, reduced duplication of effort, enhanced cross-border collaboration, and an inclusive research environment.

In summary, ESG's contributions to EOSC integration, socio-economic equity, and strategic policy alignment are multi-dimensional and enduring. By embedding FAIR and open science principles into its technical framework and delivering services that are interoperable, inclusive, and sustainable, ESG has addressed research challenges in Europe.

¹⁹ <https://training.galaxyproject.org/>

3.4 Adoption by scientific communities

The ESG project made significant scientific contributions by enabling researchers across disciplines to conduct data-intensive research with ease, transparency, and reproducibility. By improving the Galaxy platform and deploying a distributed Pulsar Network, ESG offered scalable, FAIR-compliant computational environments suitable for complex analyses—eliminating the need for local infrastructure or specialized programming skills.

The project closely collaborated with scientific communities in biodiversity, climate science, astrophysics, materials science, and life sciences (Dadras et al. 2025). ESG developed and disseminated domain-specific workflows through WorkflowHub, enabling researchers to integrate and analyze diverse datasets efficiently. For example, environmental scientists used ESG to model ecosystems and climate dynamics, while astrophysicists conducted multi-messenger analyses involving gravitational waves and neutrinos. Materials scientists benefited from ESG’s capabilities in running simulations and data processing tasks in muon spectroscopy. In the life sciences, ESG supported reproducible genomics and microbiome research aligned with FAIR principles.

These scientific communities served as demonstrator cases, directly informing ESG’s technical development and enhancing platform relevance. Additionally, the systematic integration of FDOs and the publication of reproducible workflows—equipped with PIDs, rich metadata, and provenance information—substantially improved transparency, reuse, and long-term reproducibility of research outputs.

Through these efforts, ESG not only demonstrated real-world applicability but also lowered barriers to computing infrastructure for thousands of scientists. It reinforced Europe’s global leadership in open, data-driven research by operationalizing EOSC-aligned practices in scientific workflow sharing and infrastructure federation.

4. Data Management

4.1 FAIR Data Practices and Policies

The ESG project integrated the FAIR principles throughout its data lifecycle management, embedding these principles into its Data Management Plan (Erleben, Schaaf, D’Anna, et al. 2023) from the start. ESG aligned its data policies with European Union and national regulations, ensuring compliance, openness, and the long-term usability of all produced research outputs.

To ensure findability, ESG assigned PIDs—such as Digital Object Identifiers (DOIs) via Zenodo and WorkflowHub—to project outputs, such as deliverables, workflows, and training materials. Structured metadata standards, including DataCite, Bioschemas, and RO-Crate profiles, were consistently applied to ensure rich, machine-actionable descriptions of each asset. This approach significantly enhanced discoverability through integration with repositories and search platforms such as OpenAIRE and EOSC Resource Catalogues.

Regarding accessibility, ESG adopted an open-by-default policy, ensuring all outputs—including software tools, workflows, documentation, and training resources—were freely accessible through trusted repositories like GitHub, Zenodo, and WorkflowHub. ESG implemented standardized access protocols, such as HTTPS and REST APIs, guaranteeing reliable, barrier-free access aligned with open science practices. The Galaxy platform’s native features further supported open sharing, clear versioning, and straightforward citation of workflows, thereby simplifying reuse.

Finally, ESG’s commitment to reusability was reflected through detailed documentation, clear versioning, and transparent licensing (e.g., BSD, MIT, and CC-BY). Each asset, particularly workflows published via WorkflowHub, included provenance information, execution context, and changelogs, supporting long-term reproducibility across diverse research environments. ESG’s participation in community resources like ELIXIR’s RDMkit further disseminated best practices for FAIR data management throughout Europe.

4.2 Data Sharing and Reuse

Data sharing and reuse were critical to ESG’s Open Science approach. All project-generated research outputs, including computational workflows, software tools, documentation, and training materials, were openly and responsibly shared via reputable repositories such as Zenodo, GitHub, WorkflowHub, Galaxy Tool Shed, and the GTN.

Scientific datasets referenced or utilized within ESG workflows—spanning areas such as biodiversity, climate sciences, astrophysics, and materials science—were sourced primarily from publicly licensed archives like Copernicus and GenomeArk, or securely accessed through federated infrastructures when sensitive. ESG’s innovative BYOS and BYOC models enabled secure processing of restricted datasets without compromising reproducibility or scientific rigor.

Workflow reuse was central to ESG’s approach. Over 20 FAIR-aligned workflows were published via WorkflowHub, each enriched with comprehensive metadata structured in accordance with RO-Crate and Bioschemas standards, ensuring their discoverability,

adaptability, and interoperability across EOSC-compliant platforms. To further support community-wide adoption, ESG provided onboarding materials, comprehensive tutorials, practical configuration examples, and domain-specific application scenarios through workshops and GTN contributions. This ensured that data and workflows were not only openly accessible but practically reusable by the broader research community.

4.3 Long-term Data Stewardship

To ensure long-term sustainability and accessibility of data and workflows produced by ESG, the project implemented a stewardship strategy grounded in community-trusted repositories, clear governance structures, and EOSC sustainability objectives.

All publicly shared ESG outputs, including workflows, software components, training resources, and detailed technical documentation, were deposited in reliable, open-access repositories—primarily Zenodo, WorkflowHub, GitHub, and the Galaxy ToolShed. These platforms provide persistent storage, DOI assignment, clear version control, and compliance with EU open science mandates. Metadata was structured in a way that facilitated future integration and harvesting by federated EOSC infrastructures and services.

To sustain resource usability, ESG outputs were integrated under established governance models supported by usegalaxy.eu, ELIXIR Nodes, EGI infrastructures, and partner institutions committed to ongoing maintenance, updates, and user support beyond project duration. ESG also coordinated closely with major European initiatives to maintain interoperability, avoiding fragmentation and ensuring long-term integration into the evolving EOSC ecosystem.

Furthermore, ESG's training materials and onboarding guides were designed for community formation, allowing ongoing contributions and updates to keep resources relevant and useful over time. ESG's stewardship approach thus ensures outputs remain future-proof, interoperable, and sustainably embedded within Europe's broader open research landscape.

5. Sustainability and Exploitation Plans

5.1 Long-term Hosting and Service Maintenance

ESG adopted a sustainable, distributed approach for long-term service hosting and maintenance, building upon robust institutional, national, and community infrastructure commitments across Europe. Core services—including Galaxy instances, Pulsar endpoints, workflow repositories, and training platforms—are maintained through

institutional and national infrastructures with clear long-term support strategies aligned with EOSC standards.

The central European Galaxy instance (usegalaxy.eu) continues to be reliably hosted and maintained by Albert-Ludwigs-Universität Freiburg. Additional national Galaxy instances established during ESG (including those in France, Italy, Belgium, Norway, and Spain) operate under local institutional mandates, ensuring sustained infrastructure support.

Pulsar endpoints are hosted and operated by partner institutions within a robust federated network. The automated deployment toolkit developed during ESG facilitates ongoing growth and straightforward maintenance, reducing long-term administrative burdens. WorkflowHub and Zenodo, utilized for FAIR workflow publishing, remain independently maintained by their respective communities and infrastructures. Training materials continue to be updated through the Galaxy Training Network, ensuring that resources remain accurate, accessible, and relevant.

This distributed, open governance approach assures the ongoing sustainability of ESG services and their continued evolution in alignment with EOSC's strategic vision.

5.2 Governance and funding model

ESG's governance model was designed for transparency, robustness, and sustainability beyond the initial funding period. It leverages existing institutional and national structures within the Galaxy community, ELIXIR Nodes, and EOSC-aligned infrastructures to distribute governance responsibilities across multiple stakeholders.

Operational governance responsibilities, including infrastructure maintenance and technical service development, are sustained by institutional leads and national operators. The Project Management Unit established during ESG acts as a coordination layer, facilitating continuous communication and alignment of technical strategies across partners.

From a funding perspective, ESG promotes cost-sharing and in-kind contributions. Institutional partners provide dedicated technical and operational support within national research infrastructure strategies. Further funding opportunities are actively pursued via EOSC calls, national research infrastructure schemes, and inclusion in national infrastructure roadmaps. ESG services are also strategically positioned for integration within broader EOSC offerings, ensuring flexible and sustainable funding mechanisms for continued service delivery.

5.3 Exploitation by Beneficiaries and Stakeholders

The outcomes of the ESG project are being exploited by its consortium members and a broad network of stakeholders, including research infrastructures, academic institutions, national service providers, and scientific user communities. This exploitation is taking place both within the formal scope of ESG and beyond it, as tools, methods, and workflows developed by the project.

Several ESG beneficiaries have directly incorporated the technical and service components of the project into their existing infrastructures. For instance, many partners now operate national Galaxy instances and Pulsar endpoints, offering continued support to local research communities in fields such as genomics, environmental sciences, astrophysics, and materials research. These national deployments have been integrated within institutional IT strategies and, in some cases, aligned with national digital infrastructure roadmaps or ELIXIR Node activities, ensuring their continued relevance and funding.

ESG's contributions to workflow management—particularly the adoption of RO-Crate metadata packaging and WorkflowHub integration—are supporting FAIR data practices across multiple scientific disciplines and infrastructure platforms.

The project's extensive training materials, onboarding guides, and support resources are also being used by institutions and individual trainers. These resources have been integrated into the GTN and are re-used in workshops, courses, and digital skills training programs throughout Europe. As such, ESG continues to contribute to workforce development and capacity-building efforts in data-intensive science.

Beyond the direct beneficiaries, ESG's outcomes are also being exploited by a broader set of stakeholders. Policy makers and EOSC governance bodies benefit from ESG's operationalization of FAIR principles, identity federation, and sustainable service models. Scientific communities rely on ESG workflows and training materials to conduct research more efficiently and transparently. Developers and infrastructure providers make use of ESG's deployment and monitoring tools to align their services with EOSC standards. These varied exploitation paths ensure that ESG's technical, scientific, and socio-economic contributions will continue to deliver value well beyond the project's formal duration.

6. Dissemination and Communication Activities

6.1 Key Dissemination Channels and Results

The ESG project executed a comprehensive dissemination strategy (Erleben, Schaaf, Marchis, et al. 2023), carefully designed to engage a diverse set of stakeholders—including researchers, infrastructure providers, policymakers, and the broader public. The dissemination approach combined digital platforms, open-access repositories, academic publications, and focused outreach events, maximizing visibility, stakeholder engagement, and uptake of project outputs.

The central hub for dissemination activities was the dedicated ESG webpage²⁰ hosted on the Galaxy Project website. This site provided regular project updates, deliverables, success stories, training events, and key announcements, ensuring continuous visibility and serving as the primary gateway for stakeholder engagement.

Throughout the project duration, ESG published over 150 targeted news entries, event updates, and announcements on this website, highlighting significant milestones such as infrastructure deployments, new workflows, scientific achievements, and community events. This ongoing communication maintained ESG's visibility within the research community.

To contextualize ESG's achievements within the wider research infrastructure community, partners authored multiple peer-reviewed scientific and technical publications and actively participated in major international conferences and workshops. These activities clearly positioned ESG's contributions within the broader dialogue on research infrastructures, reinforcing its reputation as a key EOSC-aligned initiative.

6.2 Community and Stakeholder Engagement

Proactive engagement with communities and stakeholders was a key factor of ESG's successful implementation. The project targeted a wide array of stakeholders—including domain-specific scientific communities, infrastructure providers, training professionals, policymakers, and individual researchers—to effectively shape service design and deployment across diverse scientific domains and regions.

ESG effectively onboarded several targeted scientific communities across diverse domains, including biodiversity, climate sciences, astrophysics, and materials science. Tailored support included domain-specific Galaxy subdomains, integrated tools, relevant

²⁰ <https://galaxyproject.org/projects/esg/>

datasets, and specially developed workflows, ensuring alignment with community needs and promoting real-world applicability.

Capacity-building was a core focus of ESG, demonstrated through comprehensive training programs involving over 10,000 participants via online and onsite workshops. The use of TaaS improved the quality and accessibility of training delivery by providing pre-configured computational environments for participants and trainers. These training resources, hosted within the Galaxy Training Network, continue to evolve, promoting long-term usability and further dissemination.

ESG partners regularly participated in scientific events, hackathons, workshops, and conferences—such as Galaxy European Days and ELIXIR meetings—to disseminate results, engage actively with the scientific community, and incorporate user feedback into platform improvements. Additionally, ESG maintained open, responsive communication channels such as mailing lists, public forums, and GitHub repositories, ensuring transparency, community participation, and continual refinement of services and workflows.

6.3 Visibility and Outreach

Visibility and broader outreach were main goals of ESG's dissemination plan, ensuring that project outcomes reached the widest possible audience, including researchers, policymakers, infrastructure providers, and the general public. ESG actively promoted its role as an enabler of FAIR, accessible, and scalable research through targeted outreach campaigns and regular presence at significant scientific events.

The central ESG webpage on the Galaxy Project site acted as a stable, publicly accessible resource, hosting updates, deliverables, events, and success stories. Regular social media campaigns and dedicated newsletters—including the Galaxy Community Newsletter, which reaches more than 100,000 global subscribers—significantly amplified project visibility, announcing new services, community achievements, and major milestones.

ESG partners presented at over 30 international conferences and community meetings, such as the EOSC Symposium, ELIXIR All-Hands meetings, and domain-specific workshops. These events elevated ESG's visibility, enhanced credibility, and fostered strategic collaboration with key EOSC-related initiatives and European research communities.

Finally, ESG's research outputs and technological achievements were disseminated through scientific publications, blogs, and open-access journals, placing ESG's work

within a broader EOSC and Horizon Europe context. Continuous engagement with EOSC governance bodies and active participation in EOSC task forces further reinforced ESG's prominent role as a model for federated, FAIR-aligned service delivery within the European research infrastructure landscape.

7. Conclusions

The ESG project has successfully delivered a federated, FAIR-compliant research infrastructure tailored to the needs of data-intensive science across Europe. By enhancing the Galaxy platform and deploying a distributed Pulsar network, ESG has enabled scalable, secure, and interoperable access to compute and storage resources.

Key innovations such as BYOC and BYOS, a smart job-scheduling system, and integration of federated authentication mechanisms have significantly improved the usability and efficiency of research workflows. ESG's integration of FDOs and contribution to WorkflowHub's maturity further advanced the discoverability and reuse of scientific workflows across domains.

Extensive training programs, community onboarding strategies, and active participation in events have strengthened ESG's user base and ensured broad adoption. Through a distributed governance model and institutional commitments, the project has established a robust foundation for long-term sustainability.

Through its alignment with EOSC principles and strategic objectives, ESG has established a sustainable and interoperable infrastructure that serves as a model for federated service delivery and the practical implementation of FAIR data practices across European research.

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